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Original Article

Accessibility and Affordability of Water Services Among Low-Income Households in Mogadishu, Somalia: The Role of Displacement and Socioeconomic Factors

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Access to safe, reliable, and affordable water remains a pressing challenge in Mogadishu, Somalia, particularly among low-income and displaced populations. This study investigates household-level water accessibility and affordability and employed a quantitative cross-sectional survey design and collected data from 384 low-income households selected through stratified random sampling across four districts in Mogadishu. A structured questionnaire was used, and data were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, t-tests, and multiple linear regression. Reliability analysis confirmed strong internal consistency of the scales (Cronbach's alpha > 0.70). Descriptive findings revealed that while households reported relatively high physical access to water, concerns persisted regarding frequent interruptions and limited confidence in future availability. Affordability emerged as a critical barrier, with most households spending more than 3–5% of their income on water and reporting difficulty paying bills on time. Inferential analyses highlighted that internally displaced persons (IDPs) experience significantly lower accessibility than non-IDPs ($p < 0.001$), while income strongly predicted affordability ($\beta = 0.34, p < 0.001$). Water price was a significant predictor of accessibility but not affordability in multivariate analysis. These findings underscore the compounded effects of displacement, low income, and high tariffs in limiting the realisation of the human right to water in Mogadishu. Policy implications include the need for targeted subsidies, lifeline tariffs, and stronger regulatory oversight to ensure equity and sustainability in water provision.

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Highlights

- First study on water access and affordability among Mogadishu’s low-income households.
- Internally displaced persons face significantly lower water accessibility.
- Affordability is the key barrier, with 70% spending above international thresholds.
- Income and displacement status are strong predictors of affordability.
- Recommends targeted subsidies, lifeline tariffs, and stronger regulation.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Figure 1: Graphical Abstract

INTRODUCTION

Access to essential resources is a cornerstone of human dignity and well-being. Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights underscores the right to an adequate standard of living for individuals and families, encompassing health, food, housing, and social services (UN General Assembly, 1948). Although water is not explicitly mentioned in this foundational document, the recognition of its importance evolved. In 2010, the United Nations General Assembly adopted Resolution 64/292, formally acknowledging access to safe and clean drinking water and sanitation as a fundamental human right indispensable to the realisation of all other rights (UN General Assembly, 2010).

The water right is widely understood through four interrelated dimensions: physical accessibility, economic accessibility, non-discrimination, and information accessibility (UN CESCR, 2003). Physical accessibility requires that water facilities be reasonably close to places of residence, work, or education, while also considering cultural and privacy needs. Economic accessibility ensures that water prices do not compromise access to other essential needs. The principle of non-discrimination safeguards equitable access for all, especially marginalised populations, and information accessibility guarantees the right of communities to receive and share clear, relevant data on water availability, quality, and management.

Between 2000 and 2022, the world's population grew from 6.1 billion to 8 billion, during which time 2.1 billion people gained access to safely managed drinking water, including 687 million since 2015. However, as of 2022, 2.2 billion people still lacked such access, with large segments relying on basic, limited, unimproved, or surface water sources (UNICEF & WHO, 2023).

Africa faces particular affordability challenges in water provision. In 2005, utility charges in many African countries ranged from 0.40 to 0.80 United

States Dollars (US\$) per cubic metre, with subsequent increases pushing rates in places like South Africa and Namibia beyond US\$1 per cubic metre. While these tariffs generally cover basic operational costs, they are insufficient for long-term infrastructure development. Cost recovery pricing of US\$1 per cubic metre, which is affordable to only 40% of households in low-income African nations which highlights the limited capacity of the majority to pay beyond US\$0.60 per cubic metre (Banerjee & Morella, 2011).

In Somalia, an estimated 6.4 million people, including 4.1 million children and 1 million women, face water shortages, particularly across 14 of the 18 regions (UNICEF Somalia, 2022). The collapse of public water systems following decades of conflict has led to reliance on unregulated private providers, whose coverage, quality, and pricing vary widely (Print *et al.*, 2013). The Banadir region, which is where Mogadishu is located, has experienced rapid population growth, further strained water infrastructure and exacerbating unsanitary conditions due to inadequate wastewater and stormwater management (Benadir Regional Administration, 2018; Bolton, 2020). Climate change adds another layer of vulnerability, affecting water quality, availability, and infrastructure resilience (Ali *et al.*, 2024).

Many low-income households, particularly in internally displaced persons (IDP) settlements, face prolonged collection times, often exceeding Sphere standards of 500 metres, and depend on untreated water (Hassen *et al.*, 2018; Saed *et al.*, 2021). The affordability dimension is equally pressing, with prices in 2019 averaging US\$1.30 per cubic meter (Jama & Mourad, 2019) and a 200-litre barrel costing US\$0.30 in 2021, equivalent to US\$1.50 per cubic metre (WASH Cluster Somalia, 2021).

Quality concerns compound the issue of affordability. Studies have found widespread public perceptions of poor water quality, including the presence of particles, unpleasant taste, and odours (Abdi-Soojeede & Kullane, 2019; Abdishakur *et al.*,

2022). The lack of regulatory oversight and proximity of latrines to water sources contribute to contamination risks. Socioeconomic factors such as education, income, and employment status strongly influence household water management practices, with low-income families less likely to treat or store water safely (Adam *et al.*, 2021).

Comparisons with other African cities highlight potential policy pathways. Nairobi and Addis Ababa implement progressive block tariffs to promote affordability for low-income households while encouraging conservation, with prices ranging from US\$0.08 to US\$0.56 per cubic metre in Addis Ababa and US\$0.31 to US\$0.55 in Nairobi (Cardenas & Whittington, 2019; Nairobi City Water and Sewerage Company, 2022). Affordability thresholds proposed by the US Environmental Protection Agency suggest that water services become burdensome when costs exceed 3–4.5% of household income (US EPA, 2024).

Furthermore, comparative insights from Galkayo, which is another Somali urban centre, reveal similar patterns of reliance on costly, informal sources, inadequate infrastructure, and absence of pro-poor pricing mechanisms (Akkaraboyina & Adem, 2018). Alternative approaches, such as rainwater harvesting, have been explored in Mogadishu, showing potential for supplementary uses but falling short of meeting total household or institutional demand (Dhaqane, 2021).

Problem Statement

Water accessibility and affordability remain critical development challenges in Mogadishu, particularly for low-income households and those residing in IDP settlements. Decades of civil conflict have undermined public water service provision, resulting in reliance on unregulated private suppliers whose prices and quality vary significantly (Print *et al.*, 2013; Jama & Mourad, 2019). High water tariffs increased from averaging US\$1.30 to US\$1.50 per cubic meter in a short time, between 2019 and 2021, respectively, placing a

disproportionate financial burden on low-income households, often exceeding internationally recognised affordability thresholds (WASH Cluster Somalia, 2021; US EPA, 2024). At the same time, public perceptions of poor water quality, including contamination risks from proximity to sanitation facilities, contribute to distrust in available sources (Abdi-Soojeede & Kullane, 2019; Abdishakur *et al.*, 2022).

The compounded effects of inadequate infrastructure, poor regulation, socio-economic inequality, and climate variability have intensified water insecurity, forcing many households to compromise on either the quantity or quality of water consumed (Ali *et al.*, 2024; Adam *et al.*, 2021). Without targeted interventions that address both affordability and safety, vulnerable populations in Mogadishu will continue to face significant barriers to achieving the human right to water as recognised by the United Nations (UN General Assembly, 2010; UN CESCR, 2003).

Knowledge Gap and Study Rationale

Limited empirical research exists on the combined effects of income, displacement status, and water pricing on access and affordability in Mogadishu. Understanding these relationships is critical for designing policies that promote equitable and sustainable urban water provision.

Research Objectives

General Objective

To investigate how socioeconomic factors (income level, displacement status, and water pricing) affect the accessibility and affordability of water services among low-income households in Mogadishu.

Specific Objectives

1. Assess overall water accessibility among low-income households in Mogadishu.
2. Evaluate perceived affordability of water services.

3. Examine the relationship between household income and affordability.
4. Compare accessibility between IDP and non-IDP residents.

5. Assess the effect of water price per cubic metre on affordability.
6. Identify key socioeconomic predictors of water accessibility and affordability.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

Research Hypotheses

- H₁: Household income is positively associated with perceived affordability of water services.
- H₂: IDPs have significantly lower water accessibility than non-IDPs.
- H₃: Higher water prices per cubic metre significantly reduce perceived affordability.
- H₄: Household income, IDP status, and water price per cubic metre significantly predict water accessibility and affordability among low-income households.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to investigate the accessibility and affordability of water services among low-income households in Mogadishu. A cross-sectional design was deemed appropriate as it allows for the systematic collection and analysis of data at a single point in time, providing a snapshot of current conditions. The quantitative approach was selected for its ability to generate standardised, measurable data, enabling statistical testing of hypothesised relationships. This approach is widely applied in service accessibility and affordability research (UN-Habitat, 2021) and was particularly suited for the structured nature of the present study.

Population and Sampling

The target population consisted of low-income households in Mogadishu, including both internally displaced persons (IDPs) living in camps and residents in formal urban settlements. A stratified random sampling technique was applied to ensure representation across socioeconomic categories and geographic locations. Stratification was based on district and IDP status, given their relevance to disparities in water access.

The sample size was 384 households, determined using Cochran’s formula for sample size estimation in large or unknown populations (Cochran, 1977). This figure provided a sufficient margin of precision at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error.

The sampling frame was drawn from four districts—Karan, Hodan, Dharkeynley, and Deynile—which were purposively selected to reflect diverse settlement types and water access conditions.

Eligibility criteria included:

- being aged 18 years or above,
- residing in a low-income household, and
- willingness to provide informed consent.

This approach ensured proportional representation of both IDP and non-IDP households, providing a balanced perspective on water access.

Figure 3: Study Area Map

Source: Study Area Map Developed by Authors 1

Data Collection Instrument

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was pre-tested on a small sample (n=30) to assess clarity, relevance, and reliability. The final instrument consisted of four sections:

- **Demographic Information:** Demographic information was collected to capture household and respondent characteristics that may influence perceptions of water access and affordability. Variables included gender, age group, marital status, education level, household monthly income, district of residence, and IDP (Internally Displaced Person) status. These factors were used both for descriptive profiling and as control variables in the analysis, helping to account for socioeconomic and contextual differences across households. Additionally, respondents were asked to report the price paid per cubic meter of water, providing a direct economic indicator for comparison across districts and income groups.
- **Water Accessibility:** Water accessibility was assessed through seven Likert-scale items that reflect key service dimensions commonly used in global monitoring frameworks. These items captured the reliability and continuity of supply, distance to the source, time required for collection, adequacy of availability when needed, water pressure, future supply security, and frequency of interruptions. Collectively, they provide a balanced view of both the physical and temporal aspects of access.
- **Water Affordability:** Affordability was evaluated using five Likert-scale items addressing both perceived and actual financial burden. The questions examined whether households considered water costs affordable, could secure sufficient quantities for daily use, and whether payments imposed financial strain or forced trade-offs with other essential needs.

Further items assessed the regularity of bill payments and whether water expenditures fell within the internationally recommended threshold of 3–5% of household income. These indicators capture a multidimensional perspective on affordability, considering both cost levels and the household's ability to sustainably meet payments.

Variables of the Study

Dependent Variables

- **Water accessibility:** Operationalised as a composite index derived from 7 Likert-scale items.
- **Water affordability:** Operationalised as a composite index derived from 5 Likert-scale items.

Independent Variables

- Household monthly income
- IDP status (IDP vs. non-IDP)
- Water price per cubic metre

These predictors were chosen based on prior empirical research and theoretical frameworks on water poverty (UNDP, 2006).

Control Variables

- Gender
- Age
- Marital status
- Educational level
- Area of residence

These demographic factors were included to control for potential confounding influences on accessibility and affordability.

Data Analysis Procedures

Data were cleaned, coded, and analysed using SPSS version 26.0. The following steps were undertaken:

- **Descriptive statistics:** Frequencies and percentages were used for categorical variables, while means and standard deviations summarised continuous variables.
- **Scale reliability testing:** Internal consistency of the accessibility and affordability indices was assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha, with values ≥ 0.70 considered acceptable (Nunnally, 1978).
- **Composite index computation:** Mean scores were calculated for accessibility and affordability indices.
- **Inferential analysis:**
 - **Pearson correlation** examined linear associations between continuous variables.
 - **Independent samples t-test** compared mean differences in accessibility and affordability between IDP and non-IDP households.

- **Multiple linear regression models** tested the predictive power of household income, IDP status, and water price per cubic metre on the dependent variables, controlling for demographic factors. Robustness checks were conducted by running the models with and without control variables to assess the stability of coefficients.

RESULTS

Reliability Analysis

Cronbach’s alpha was used to assess the internal consistency of the water accessibility and affordability scales. Both scales demonstrated acceptable reliability, with values above the recommended threshold of 0.70 (Table 1). The affordability scale ($\alpha = 0.912$) showed very high reliability, suggesting the items are strongly consistent but may be somewhat redundant. The accessibility scale ($\alpha = 0.765$) also indicated satisfactory reliability, confirming that the construct was measured adequately. These results validate the use of composite scores for subsequent analysis.

Table 1: Reliability of Scales

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
Water Accessibility	7	0.765
Water Affordability	5	0.912

Descriptive Statistics

Demographic Characteristics and Price per Metre Cubic (PPM³)

Table 2 summarises the demographic characteristics of the 384 respondents. The sample was relatively balanced in terms of gender, with females representing 54.4%. Young adults (18–30 years) constituted the largest age group (40.4%), highlighting that water challenges are being experienced primarily by a younger and economically active population.

A significant proportion of participants reported modest monthly incomes, with nearly 70% earning below \$300. This income profile is important because the majority (73.2%) reported paying \$1.50/m³ for water, a relatively high unit cost considering international affordability thresholds. Internally displaced persons (IDPs) accounted for 29.9% of the respondents, a critical subgroup given their later demonstrated disadvantages in accessibility and affordability.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents and PPM³ (N = 384)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	175	45.6%
	Female	209	54.4%
	18–30 years	155	40.4%
	31–45 years	106	27.6%
	46–60 years	114	29.7%
	> 60 years	9	2.3%
	Marital Status	Single	102
	Married	168	43.8%
	Divorced	105	27.3%
	Widowed	9	2.3%
	Education	No formal education	76
	Primary	102	26.6%
	Secondary	72	18.8%
	Tertiary	134	34.9%
Monthly Income	< \$100	48	12.5%
	\$100–200	114	29.7%
	\$201–300	107	27.9%
	\$301–400	115	29.9%
IDP Status	IDP	115	29.9%
	Non-IDP	269	70.1%
Water Price	\$1.50/m ³	281	73.2%
	\$1.60/m ³	103	26.8%

Water Accessibility

Respondents generally reported good physical access to water, with high mean scores for weekly availability ($M = 4.22$) and proximity to sources ($M = 3.98$) (Table 3). However, perceptions of long-term reliability were less positive. Confidence in future availability was moderate ($M = 3.32$), and the

low mean score on the statement “no frequent interruptions” ($M = 2.60$) indicates that many households actually experience frequent interruptions. Overall, this suggests that while day-to-day access is relatively strong, the water supply system remains unstable and prone to disruptions, raising concerns about reliability during periods of stress such as drought or displacement.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Water Accessibility (N = 384)

Item	SD (%)	D (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
1. Regular access to water throughout the week	12.2	0.5	27.9	59.4	4.22	1.29
2. Water source located close to home	9.9	12.8	24.5	52.9	3.98	1.39
3. Do not spend much time collecting water	9.6	5.5	23.2	61.7	4.22	1.29
4. Water is available whenever needed	0	22.7	53.4	24.0	3.79	1.05
5. Water pressure sufficient	0	7.6	90.4	2.1	3.87	0.55
6. Confident water available tomorrow/future	0	36.5	58.9	4.7	3.32	1.02
7. No frequent interruptions	4.7	65.6	24.5	5.2	2.60	1.07

Water Affordability

Affordability emerged as a major challenge (Table 4). Respondents consistently disagreed that water costs were affordable (M = 2.13) or that paying for water did not cause financial difficulty (M = 1.88). Less than one-third believed they could afford the amount of water their household required (M = 2.36). Furthermore, a majority reported spending

more than 3–5% of their household income on water (M = 2.01).

These findings reveal a widespread financial burden of water services, well above international benchmarks that consider water unaffordable if costs exceed 3–5% of household income. The data suggest that economic access, rather than physical access, is the primary barrier to water security in Mogadishu.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Water Affordability (N = 384)

Item	SD (%)	D (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	SD
1. Water cost is affordable	39.3	40.6	8.3	11.7	2.13	1.33
2. Can afford household water needs	37.8	26.6	33.1	2.6	2.36	1.35
3. Paying for water does not cause difficulty	45.3	39.3	13.0	2.3	1.88	1.08
4. Can pay the water bill on time	48.2	27.3	17.2	7.3	2.08	1.35
5. Spend less than 3–5% income on water	59.6	12.5	22.9	4.9	2.01	1.40

Inferential Statistics

Pearson Correlation

Income was moderately and positively correlated with affordability (r = 0.275, p < 0.001), indicating that higher-income households are more likely to perceive water as affordable. However, the moderate effect size suggests that income alone does not guarantee affordability, pointing to structural issues in water pricing.

Water price was weakly but significantly and negatively correlated with affordability (r = -0.142, p = 0.005), confirming that price increases erode

affordability, even within the narrow range of \$1.50–1.60.

Independent Samples t-Test

Significant disparities were observed between IDPs and non-IDPs in terms of water accessibility (t = -9.55, p < 0.001). Non-IDPs reported substantially higher accessibility (M = 3.92) compared to IDPs (M = 3.23). This finding highlights the structural vulnerability of displaced communities, whose access to reliable and sufficient water remains far below that of host populations, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Comparing IDPs and non-IDPs on Water Accessibility

Group	Mean Accessibility	Std. Dev.	t (df=382)	p-value
IDPs	3.23	0.995	-9.55	<0.001
Non-IDPs	3.92	0.429		

Multiple Linear Regression

Predicting Water Services Accessibility

The regression model explained 21.2% of the variance in water accessibility ($R^2 = 0.212$, $F(3, 380) = 34.16$, $p < 0.001$). IDP status was the strongest predictor ($\beta = 0.454$, $p < 0.001$), with IDPs

facing significantly poorer access. Water price also had a significant negative effect ($\beta = -0.147$, $p = 0.002$), indicating that small price increases constrain accessibility. Income did not significantly predict accessibility ($p = 0.348$), suggesting that access barriers are more structural than financial.

Table 6: Predicting Water Services Accessibility

Predictor	B	β	t	p
Constant	3.131	—	13.11	<0.001
Income (USD)	-0.034	-0.047	-0.940	0.348
IDP Status (1=Yes)	0.717	0.454	9.410	<0.001
Water Price/m ³	-0.240	-0.147	-3.070	0.002

Predicting Water Services Affordability

The model explained 13.7% of the variance in affordability ($R^2 = 0.137$, $F(3, 380) = 20.06$, $p < 0.001$). Both income ($\beta = 0.343$, $p < 0.001$) and IDP status ($\beta = -0.253$, $p < 0.001$) were significant predictors. Higher income improved affordability,

while IDP households faced greater financial strain. Water price was not significant ($p = 0.417$), suggesting that the narrow price variation is less influential than socio-economic status.

Table 7: Predicting Water Services Affordability

Predictor	B	β	t	p
Constant	2.338	—	6.029	<0.001
Income (USD)	0.378	0.343	6.483	<0.001
IDP Status (1=Yes)	-0.620	-0.253	-5.008	<0.001
Water Price/m ³	-0.103	-0.041	-0.813	0.417

Summary of Key Findings

Overall, the results show that:

- Physical accessibility is generally adequate in the short term but unreliable in the long term.
- Affordability is the critical challenge, with most households exceeding international cost benchmarks.
- IDPs consistently experience lower accessibility and affordability, highlighting

displacement as a key determinant of inequality.

- Income provides only partial protection against affordability challenges, showing that structural pricing and service delivery models need attention.
- Together, these findings emphasise that while water is physically available in Mogadishu, its financial accessibility remains inequitable, disproportionately affecting vulnerable groups such as the poor and displaced.

DISCUSSION

Water Accessibility

The study revealed that most low-income households in Mogadishu have physical access to water sources, with respondents reporting regular water availability and proximity. This supports the UN Committee on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (2003) framework, which defines physical accessibility as a key dimension of water access. However, the frequent interruptions and lower confidence in long-term water availability highlight challenges in service reliability, especially among internally displaced persons (IDPs). This aligns with Print *et al.* (2013) and Benadir Regional Administration (2018), which document the fragmented and inconsistent water supply in Mogadishu, disproportionately affecting displaced and vulnerable populations. The significant difference in accessibility between IDPs and non-IDPs underlines the compounded disadvantage IDPs face in securing reliable water services, as also noted by Saed *et al.* (2021).

Water Affordability

Affordability remains a significant barrier for many households, with over 70% spending more than the recommended 3–5% of household income on water (US EPA, 2024). This confirms findings from Banerjee & Morella (2011) and Jama & Mourad (2019), showing that water tariffs in Somalia and other African regions often exceed the financial capacity of low-income households. The study's statistical analyses showed household income as a significant predictor of perceived affordability, consistent with global evidence emphasising socioeconomic status as a determinant of water affordability (UNICEF & WHO, 2023).

Socioeconomic and Displacement Factors Affecting Access and Affordability

The findings emphasise the impact of socioeconomic and displacement status on water service outcomes. IDPs report significantly poorer water accessibility and affordability compared to non-IDPs, reflecting their increased vulnerability and limited economic means, as reported in studies by Hassen *et al.* (2018) and Mohamed (2025). Although water price per cubic metre had a negative correlation with affordability and accessibility, it was not a significant predictor when controlling for income and IDP status, suggesting that economic capacity and displacement play more critical roles. These results point to the necessity of targeted subsidies and social protection mechanisms to mitigate disparities in water access among displaced and low-income households.

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights that ensuring safe and equitable water access in Mogadishu requires more than expanding infrastructure; it demands addressing the intertwined economic and social barriers that disproportionately affect low-income and displaced households. The findings reveal that affordability is the most significant obstacle, indicating that water pricing structures and household income disparities directly influence accessibility. This has important implications for urban water governance in fragile contexts, where reliance on unregulated private vendors can exacerbate inequality and undermine public health.

To move towards inclusive and sustainable water provision, policy responses should combine infrastructure development with measures that directly reduce the financial burden on vulnerable populations. Key recommendations include introducing targeted subsidies or lifeline tariffs for low-income and IDP households, prioritising investments in underserved districts to improve reliability and quality, and implementing regulatory frameworks to monitor and control private sector

pricing. Public awareness initiatives on efficient water use and consumer rights, along with the integration of IDP needs into urban planning, are essential for building resilience and equity in Mogadishu's water sector.

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Author Contributions (optional)

- **Jamal Abdikarim Mohamed:** conceptualisation, methodology, investigation, data analysis, writing – original draft, supervision, and project administration.
- **Abdilatif Hussein Omar:** data acquisition, validation, and writing (review & editing).
- **Said Aweis Ahmed:** data curation, visualisation, and final manuscript review.
- **Abdinasir Ibrahim Mohamed:** resources, formal analysis, and writing – review & editing.

Data Availability Statement

The data of this article, including questionnaire, coded & cleaned data in Excel format, and also research articles, reports, thesis, and conference proceedings used in this article's literature can be found in this Google Drive link https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1038ysN7E2j35mRiOB0ReK4yaDTLhv2_Z, which is open access for everyone with the link. For further

information about this research article can contact the corresponding author of the article.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Ethics Statement

This research was conducted in accordance with recognised ethical standards for social science research. Ethical approval was obtained from the Somali National University and the Banadir Regional Administration prior to data collection. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents after explaining the study's objectives, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. No personal identifiers were collected to ensure anonymity, and all data were treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes. The study adhered to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and complied with applicable national and institutional guidelines on research involving human participants.

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